

UZBEKISTAN IS AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FACTORS RELATING TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE VALUES

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Annotation: In Uzbekistan, at a new stage of development, the possibilities of impartial study of the process of creating a valuable attitude to science in the mind of the young generation, organization of theoretical and methodological issues related to its philosophical understanding on a literally scientific basis, and in particular, the possibility of correctly assessing the place of science in the development of society are revealed. On the basis of thinking, a person has the opportunity to know the existence in a deep and comprehensive way. In thinking, the signs of objects and events and their legal interconnections, general and specific aspects are clearly displayed.

Key words: Innovation, ethics, medicine, biology, ecology, social development, bioethics, Moral values, Intellectual activity, invention, ability, discovery.

Introduction: In the leading scientific research institutions and scientific centers of the developed countries of the world, many studies are being conducted on the emergence of science, its development stages, ethical and axiological boundaries. In particular, the emergence of the science of bioethics in the system of philosophical sciences, not only ethics, but also the researches carried out within the framework of such sciences as medicine, biology, and ecology, gave rise to axiological debates about the similarity of the original foundations of human mental and physical existence. This created the need to reconsider the situation that has arisen in the whole world, the events of global scale, as well as the views on the inevitability of science to serve goodness. The results of modern science in Uzbekistan require intensive research and a creative approach to every issue from research scientists. At the moment, the tasks of developing science and forming an axiological attitude towards it are becoming more urgent in order to "further develop science in our country, to educate our youth as possessors of deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture" [1]. It is also related to creating an environment of axiological attitude to science in our society and defining "increasing the passion and intellectual potential of the growing young generation"[2] as important tasks.

At a new stage of development in Uzbekistan, an objective study of the process of creating a valuable attitude to science in the minds of the young generation, the organization of theoretical and methodological issues related to its philosophical understanding on a literally scientific basis, and in particular, an opportunity to correctly assess the place of science in the development of society. In this regard, in the scientific research conducted by our philosophers such as I.Mo'minov, J.Tulenov, S.Shermuhamedov, Q.Nazarov, K.O.Shaikhova, I.Soifnazarov, N.Shermuhamedova, T.Artikov, G.Tulenova [3] , as well as F.Yuldasheva, A.Kambarov, I.Siddikov[4], it is necessary to note that they showed an axiological attitude to science in the scientific research conducted by our philosophers.

In most of the studies analyzed above, the question of science, creativity, and its importance in human and social life is defined and classified epistemologically and epistemologically, not praxeologically. Also, in the above studies, they paid attention to the socio-philosophical aspects of science, the valuable nature of the scientific heritage that is its results, their importance in the formation of a well-rounded person, their importance in educating a well-rounded person. Every country is accelerating reforms to increase its scientific capabilities and create scientific progress. At the new stage of its development, Uzbekistan is also paying special attention to the tasks of forming a sense of high appreciation of science in the social environment, educating people who respect science in society. After all, "we must create all the facilities for the education of our enthusiastic young people who say they will get higher education and work on themselves"[5]. As a result of these works, the quality of education will increase and the generation of competitive personnel will be accelerated.

Currently, the problem in the center of attention of the science of philosophy is the problem of man, that is, the relationship of man to nature, society, and people to each other, consists in consciously reflecting the laws of their development. It is clear from this that the formation and development of the culture of philosophical thinking of a person is the main problem at the center of the science of philosophy.

Human thinking created a solid foundation for the emergence of science, the active application of scientific knowledge methods to the process of knowledge, and the development of fundamental sciences. Because, "It is no coincidence that scientific achievements in the world are achieved in the direction of fundamental research. Therefore, comprehensive support of fundamental sciences, provision of the field with talented young personnel is being put on the agenda as one of the important tasks of our state" [6]. Therefore, in ensuring the development of fundamental sciences, it is one of the urgent tasks to illuminate the process of science development, to form correct concepts among students of science.

In accordance with the progressive development of society, along with other types of human social activity, scientific activity related to the field of science appeared. This activity has a socio-historical character and has increasingly covered society and human life. As a result, a new type of human activity, scientific activity, and a new field of spirituality, science, appeared in the life of society. At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the tasks of developing science and appreciating science as the basis of development continue to be of great importance even today.

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